

UNIVERSITY OF
CAMBRIDGE

New insights on protoclusters in the early Universe from the JWST

Nicolas Laporte

Paris – 8th September 2023

Callum Witten, Jan Scholtz, Herve Dole, Adi Zitrin, Richard Ellis, J. Bennett et al.

Age of the Universe (Myr)

0.38

300

1 000

13 800

Big-Bang

Recombination

Dark Ages

Formation of the
First galaxies

Reionisation

TODAY

1000

10-12

6

0

Redshift

The "hunt" for the most distant galaxies *between 1950s and 2022*

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- Humason et al. 1956
- Minkowski 1960
- Spinrad et al. 1975
- Spinrad & Smith 1976
- Smith et al. 1979
- Spinrad 1982
- Spinrad & Djorgovsky 1984
- Lilly 1988
- Chambers et al. 1990
- Lacy et al. 1994
- Petitjean et al. 1996
- Franz et al. 1997
- Day et al. 1998
- Hu et al. 1999, 2002
- Pelló et al. 2004
- Iye et al. 2006
- Fontana et al. 2010
- Vanzella et al. 2011
- Ono et al. 2012
- Shibuya et al. 2012
- Finkelstein et al. 2013
- Oesch et al 2014
- Zitrin et al. 2015
- Oesch et al. 2016
- Harikane et al. 2022
- Curtis-Lake et al. 2023

The "hunt" for the most distant galaxies between 1950s and 2022

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 Minkowski 1960
 Spinrad et al. 1975
 Spinrad & Smith 1976
 Smith et al. 1979
 Spinrad 1982
 Spinrad & Djorgovsky 1984
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Our view of the most distant galaxies pre-JWST

Ishigaki et al. (2018)

- High-redshift galaxies are extremely faint therefore, to detect them one needs to use gravitational lensing.
- The HST flagship program using lensing was the *Hubble Frontier Fields* program (Lotz et al. 2017)
- Even with lensing the deepest magnitude we can reach was AB \sim 29 (5σ)

- We were focussing on the brightest population of galaxies at very high-redshift
- The spectroscopic confirmation of all $z \geq 8$ galaxies was difficult because of the absorption of Ly- α by the neutral IGM.
- The study of their environment was not feasible, and the identification of real proto-cluster limited.

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The arrival of the *James Webb* Space Telescope

25th December 2021 – Kourou (French Guyana)

12th July 2022

Within the first month after the release of the first images

TIMELINE OF THE FIRST PAPERS

Number of publication submitted each day on Astro-pH/galaxies

ERO SMACS0723
ERS GLASS

ERS CEERS
Lensing

Comissioning data

Within the first month after the release of the first images

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- 21st July 22 : Schaerer et al. (2022)
- 22nd July 22 : Suess et al. (2022)
- 25th July 22 : Adams et al. (2022) ; Leethochawalit et al. (2022)

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- 21st July 22 : Schaerer et al. (2022)
- 22nd July 22 : Suess et al. (2022)
- 25th July 22 : Adams et al. (2022) ; Leethochawalit et al. (2022)
- 26th July 22 : Atek et al. (2022) ; Roberts-Borsani et al. (2022) ; Trump et al. (2022) ; Curti et al. (2022) ; Sun et al. (2022) ; Donnan et al. (2022) ; Chen et al. (2022) ; Yan et al. (2022) ; Morishita et al. (2022) ; Santini et al. (2022), Merlin et al. (2022)

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The first extragalactic survey : SMACS0723

HUBBLE

- SMACS0723 was previously observed with *Hubble* in the framework of the RELICS survey (Salmon et al. 2020)
- 11 galaxies at $z \geq 6$ were identified, including 2 at $z \sim 7$ and 0 at $z \geq 8$

The first extragalactic survey : SMACS0723

- SMACS0723 was previously observed with *Hubble* in the framework of the RELICS survey (Salmon et al. 2020)
 - 11 galaxies at $z \geq 11$ were identified, including 2 at $z \sim 7$ and 0 at $z \geq 8$
-
- *James Webb* observed this cluster as part of its Early Release Observations (ERO) program in both imaging and spectroscopy
 - Images reach a depth of 29.5AB at 5σ (2hrs/band) ; spectra reach a sensitivity of 3×10^{-18} erg/s/cm² (2.5hrs)

The first extragalactic survey : SMACS0723

Salmon et al. (2020)

The 2 galaxies at $z \sim 7$ previously identified with HST were selected for spectroscopic observations with JWST

The first extragalactic survey : SMACS0723

Salmon et al. (2020)

The 2 galaxies at $z \sim 7$ previously identified with HST were selected for spectroscopic observations with JWST

Laporte et al. (2022)

- Their spectroscopic redshifts have not been confirmed with the usual emission line ($\text{Ly}\alpha$) but with optical lines (e.g., [OIII]4959,5007)
- Both are at the same redshift $z = 7.66$ and are separated by less than $3''$ (15kpc)

- The probability of having two non-interacting galaxies at the same redshift outside an over-dense environment is very low.

Search for $z \sim 7.5$ galaxies behind SMACS0723

Chiang et al. (2017)

- With one JWST pointing [2 x (2.2'x2.2')] one can only cover 0.72 Mpc² (at $z = 7$) that is much smaller than the expected size for protocluster.

- However, protocluster core will be fully covered by one JWST NIRCам pointing.
- We applied the LBG technique in a 40''x40'' box to search for other candidates in the vicinity of the 2 spectroscopically confirmed galaxies

We identified 8 galaxies, including the 2 spectroscopically confirmed galaxies, with similar colors and F150W magnitude ranging from 26.0 to 28.5 AB

Laporte et al. (2022)

Search for $z \sim 7.5$ galaxies behind SMACS0723

- We used SED-fitting technique to estimate the photometric redshift as well as physical properties (mass, sfr, etc.) of our candidates
- Stacking all $P(z)$ shows a peak at $z \sim 7.7$.
- As a sanity check, we compute the photometric redshift in our search box and in the entire field. An overdensity is clearly detected at $z \sim 7.7$.

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Physical properties of this protocluster candidate

Method	Estimated $M_h [M_\odot]$
Summing all M_h	$3.34^{+0.59}_{-0.50} \times 10^{11} M_\odot$
Baryonic to dark matter ratio from Planck	$6.52^{+2.82}_{-1.85} \times 10^{10} M_\odot$
From the most massive galaxy	$6.86^{+2.51}_{-2.42} \times 10^{10} M_\odot$
Stellar-to-halo mass ratio (Shuntov+2022)	$2.07 \pm 1.51 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$

- From SED_fitting, we can plot the SFR vs M_* plot of the protocluster members. They are all following the main sequence at $z \sim 7$
- We estimate the dark matter halo mass of the protocluster using several methods. They all agree with a mass of
$$M_h \sim 1 - 3 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$$

Physical properties of this protocluster candidate

The estimated dark matter halo mass seems consistent with what is expected for the evolution of a Coma-like cluster at $z \sim 7.7$

Its properties seems also comparable with other protoclusters observed before the arrival of JWST

Adapted from Remus et al. (2023)

Further spectroscopic analysis

Feltre et al. (2016)

Brinchmann (2023)

Without X-Rays observation, one can identify AGN with the detection of high ionising potential emission lines.

The detection of NeIV in one of our protocluster members suggest that this object may host an AGN. However, deeper data are needed to confirm this claim.

KMOS observation on going. So far only ~30% of the data has been obtained

NIRCam grism spectroscopy in Cycle 2 to confirm protocluster members.

A protocluster at even higher redshift ? The interesting case of GNz11

Bunker et al. (2023), Maiolino et al. (2023)

Detection of NeIV tracing high gas density ($>10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$)

The most distant galaxy identified by the Hubble Space Telescope host a massive black hole (although there is still an active debate) just ~ 400 Myr after the Big-Bang

This super-massive black hole ($\sim 3 \times 10^6 M_{\odot}$) may have been accreting at super-Eddington over the last 100 Myr and could have originated from a stellar mass seeds at $z \sim 15$

A protocluster at even higher redshift ? The interesting case of GNz11

Deep NIRCам observations of GOODS-North show that 9 objects with similar colors (and therefore similar photometric redshift) are in the NIRCам field-of-view.

This corresponds to ~ 5 comoving Mpc.

A protocluster at even higher redshift ?

The interesting case of GNz11

Scholtz et al. (2023)

Recent DDT observations with NIRSpec-IFU/JWST shows that several Ly- α emitters are detected in the vicinity of GNz11 (the most distant object with detected Ly- α)

A preliminary analysis of this field shows that the overdensity parameter is at least 27, the densest field at such high-redshift

More JWST observation to follow in February 2024 !

A protocluster at even higher redshift ?

The interesting case of GNz11

Scholtz et al. (2023)

Adapted from Remus et al. (2023)

Summary and Conclusions

“Everything now is in protocluster !”

- *Hubble* was limited to the study and analysis of the brightest galaxies in the early Universe (*the tip of the iceberg*)
- When the *Webb* re-observes *Hubble* selected galaxies, it seems to identify many more galaxies with similar colors (same z ?)
- 3 protoclusters at $z > 7$ have been identified with *Webb* (including one spectroscopically confirmed – see Takahiro’s talk)
- All these clusters seems to have properties consistent with what is expected by simulations at $z > 7$
- Two of them host an AGN candidate, that makes the case even more interesting.

